

Grant Agreement Number: 723265

Project acronym: **Clusters 2.0**

Project full title: Clusters 2.0 - Open network of hyper connected logistics clusters towards Physical Internet

D.4.4.

Reliable train-truck horizontal transshipment Prototype – Interim Evaluation Report

Due delivery date: 25/07/2018

Actual delivery date: 25/07/2018

Organization name of lead participant for this deliverable:

Project co-funded by the European Commission within Horizon 2020		
Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014 – 2020)

Document Control Sheet

Deliverable number:	4.4.
Deliverable responsible:	Innovatrain AG
Work package:	4
Editor:	Pieter van den Bold

Author(s) – in alphabetical order		
Name	Organisation	E-mail
Pieter van den Bold	Innovatrain AG	p.vdbold@innovatrain.ch

Document Revision History			
Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
V1	07.05.2018		
V1.1	27.05.2018	Improvements in layout	IML
V 1.2	20.07.2018	Small Adaptations to the text	Innova

Abstract

Legal Disclaimer

The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that the information is fit for any particular purpose. The above referenced consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law. © 2017 by Clusters 2.0 Consortium.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
PO	Project officer
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	5
2. Status Quo of horizontal transshipment process until 2017	7
2.1 ContainerMover 3020: mayor parts explained	7
2.2 Horizontal Transshipment in sequence (steps), status 2017	10
2.3 Next steps to come to fully automatic transshipment.....	14
3. Development of full automation of transshipment	15
3.1 Introduction.....	15
3.2 First the horizontal distance measuring	16
3.3 Introduction of an “intelligent” Camera.....	17
4. Full automatic horizontal transshipment	20
4.1 New process of automatic horizontal transshipment	20
5. Conclusion	22

List of Figures

Figure 1 – ContainerMover 3000 controlled by wireless remote control	5
Figure 2 – type of containers for the CM 3020.....	7
Figure 3 – Wagon adaptor frame on 20’ position.....	8
Figure 4 – the mayor parts of the CM3020 Module	8
Figure 5 – The two “contact bridges” between truck and railway wagon.....	9
Figure 6 – CM-4000 for weights up to 35 tons (45’ container).....	9
Figure 7 – Wagon adaptor with “cross hairs sign” for positioning.....	10
Figure 8 – Screen shot (ready for transshipment)	11
Figure 9 – The remote control, the driver is using	11
Figure 10 – 8 Steps to shift a container from the ContainerMover to the wagon	12
Figure 11 – 8 Steps to shift a container from the wagon to the ContainerMover	13
Figure 12 – The contact bridge between ContainerMover and Wagon Adaptor	14
Figure 13 – Adjusting the height of the two “contact bridges”.....	15
Figure 14 – The screen in the cab and one of the ultrasonic sensors.....	16
Figure 15 – the linear encoder for measuring the exact distance the contract bridge is ejected.	16
Figure 16 – “dry tests” of the camera and software	17
Figure 17 – field test of camera and software.....	18
Figure 18 – Industry camera Baumer VCXG-53M.I.....	18
Figure 19 –ContainerMover with two high solution cameras and two ultrasonic sensors	19
Figure 20 – high solution cameras and the infra-red support light.....	19
Figure 21 – Wagon adaptor with “cross hairs sign” for positioning.....	20
Figure 22 – Process of Positioning the ContainerMover-Truck at the railway wagon	20
Figure 23 – starting transshipment	21
Figure 24 – Process of automatic transshipment.....	21
Figure 25 – lay out of the screen in the cab.....	22

Executive Summary

The horizontal transshipment process is seen by Clusters 2.0 as one of the enablers to shift containers to rail also at smaller distribution terminals (goal: low capital and infrastructure Investment loading and unloading systems for small intermodal terminals), it is clear that the technique must be low-cost, reliable and easy to use.

The purpose of 4.4. is to make the horizontal transshipment technique more reliable and more easy to use by further automating the transshipment process being in line with the NMLU developments. Purpose of this deliverable is to document the demonstration of a new automatic transshipment technology that will be used for testing NMLU in an intermodal operation scenario to a later stage of the project.

The first model of the Innovatrain ContainerMover 3000 for horizontal transshipment, which came out in 2012, was operated by a state of the art wireless remote control enabling the driver of the truck to initiate and control all movements of the transshipment by remote control. Operational experience with a first series of ContainerMovers learnt that this great freedom of controlling all movements by the driver was also a possible source for errors and incorrect use of the technique, causing damages and greater tear and wear to the equipment.

As Innovatrain had already realized the automation of parts of the process, we have concentrated on the automation of the remaining manual steps of the transshipment process with the purpose to create one loop of sequential processes to perform the whole transshipment.

This goal is finally reached by tackling the most difficult part: recognizing and detecting the position of Wagon-Adaptor on the railway wagon in relation to the position of the ContainerMover truck.

The solution is based on using the method of digital image reading with a special camera in combination with image processing software. The software is able to deliver an accurate relative position of the camera against an object it sees and as a result we were able to automatically position the so called “contact bridges” on the wagon.

The driver still has to steer the truck to the indicated position at the train and after initiating the parking brake, he can start the automatic transshipment. During the performance of the transshipment, the driver needs to actively push and hold the joystick on his remote control in the forward position. When the driver releases the joystick, the movements immediately stop. In this way, the safety of the process can be guaranteed.

Fully automated horizontal transshipment is technically possible due to the capability of the ContainerMover to recognize its relative position to the wagon adaptor both in a horizontal as vertical way.

1. Introduction

The horizontal transshipment process is seen by Clusters 2.0 as one of the enablers to shift containers to rail also at smaller distribution terminals (goal: low capital and infrastructure Investment loading and unloading systems for small intermodal terminals), it is clear that the technique must be low-cost, reliable and easy to use.

The purpose of 4.4. is to make the horizontal transshipment technique more reliable and more easy to use by further automating the transshipment process being in line with the NMLU developments. Purpose of this deliverable is to document the demonstration of a new automatic transshipment technology that will be used for testing NMLU in an intermodal operation scenario to a later stage of the project.

ContainerMover 3000

Innovatrain AG develops and markets innovative technical solutions;

- for intermodal freight transport by rail (especially to help shift time critical (FMGC) products from road to rail, at lower daily volumes and in situations where there is a lack of operational space), and
- for on-site container logistics and transshipment of containers.

Figure 1 – ContainerMover 3000 controlled by wireless remote control

The horizontal transshipment technology by Innovatrain has been continuously developed further since the beginning in 2012, starting with a version for the transshipment of smaller units like the C745 swap body and the 20 foot standard container, up to the model CM-4000

for heavy and large containers (30' - 45' and up to 34 tons), available in 2019.

The first model of the ContainerMover 3000, which came out in 2012, was operated by a state of the art wireless remote control enabling the driver of the truck to initiate and control all movements of the transshipment by remote control.

Operational experience with the ContainerMover technique at customers during 2012-2015 showed that this great freedom of controlling all movements by the driver was also a possible source for errors and incorrect use of the technique, causing damages and greater tear and wear to the equipment.

During the period 2016-2017, Innovatrain was able to automate part of the horizontal movement and to build in checks and controls so that the transshipment process became much more controlled and smooth, however the goal of a full-automated horizontal transshipment was not yet reached.

As the horizontal transshipment process is seen by Clusters 2.0 as one of the enablers to shift containers to rail also at smaller distribution terminals, it is clear that the technique must be low-cost, reliable and easy to use.

The advantages of a full-automated horizontal transshipment are:

- suppress human errors due to inexperience and distraction of the operational personnel,
- control the movement forces on the equipment,
- adjust movement speeds to optimal values,
- Install electronic interfaces with operational site software to receive orders and to deliver performance data back (container number, weight, slot number on train, etc.)
- opening the possibility to combine the transshipment technology with AGVs (Automated Guided Vehicles) in order to arrive at completely automated transshipment processes on local terminals.

The aim of the task of WP 4.4 will be that the driver of the ContainerMover will transport the full-size containers between plant and train, but the actual transshipment at the train will be done completely automated by the vehicle itself.

The intention was to automate all remaining steps of the transshipment process, which are still manually initiated and controlled via remote control.

The steps of the positioning process of the truck at the railway wagon are not part of the project.

The reason for this is that:

1. we don't have the authorization to make changes / extensions to the steering of the truck,
2. there are several different suppliers of trucks, with different systems, and
3. the truck manufacturers are already strongly involved in programs for self-driving / self-steering trucks.

We have therefore fully concentrated on the automation of the remaining manual steps of the transshipment process.

This document describes the technology and key process for automating horizontal transshipment processes in an intermodal scenario as demonstrated in a test trial in Bern, Switzerland in Spring 2018.

2. Status Quo of horizontal transshipment process until 2017

2.1 ContainerMover 3020: mayor parts explained

The ContainerMover 3020 System is a new and revolutionary way of loading and unloading containers on trains. A truck with a ContainerMover 3020 System is capable of the direct horizontal transfer of standard containers like:

Standard 20' containers

Standard swap-bodies
(EN-Norm: 7.45 m / 7.15 m / 7.82 m)

Figure 2 – type of containers for the CM 3020

- ✓ The same truck you use for transport and distribution is used to transfer a container in just 3 minutes to and from the railway wagon. The system is operated by a remote control.
- ✓ You only need a road or asphalted area of minimum 3 meters width, parallel to the railway-tracks.

Dependent on the truck dimensions, the Container-Mover 3020 can transfer weights up to 18 tons.

The 3-axle truck, equipped with a ContainerMover-system, is capable of transporting up to 16 tons.

Clusters 2.0

- ✓ On the wagon, a simple steel frame is mounted. This frame has the size of a 20' container and is fixed on the normal 20'-container-pins of the container-wagon.

Figure 3 – Wagon adaptor frame on 20' position

ContainerMover 3020 Module

The main device is the ContainerMover module which is to be mounted on a truck-chassis.

It is build up the following way:

Two **mover-panels** with **mover-beams**, lift the container using hydraulic and pneumatic power.

Then the hydraulic powered chain system moves the container horizontally from the truck to the container wagon or vice versa.

Figure 4 – the mayor parts of the CM3020 Module

Contact Bridges

The Container Mover is equipped with two “contact bridges”, equipped with steel rolls, which actually form the transfer bridges between truck and railway wagon. These bridges support the container during the horizontal transfer.

Figure 5 – The two “contact bridges” between truck and railway wagon

ContainerMover 4000 Module

In 2018, the prototype of the CM-4000 will be build. This module will be capable to transfer containers with weights up to 35 tons. The functioning and steering of the system will be the same as for the CM 3020.

Figure 6 – CM-4000 for weights up to 35 tons (45' container)

2.2 Horizontal Transshipment in sequence (steps), status 2017

The sequence of the horizontal transshipment steps, after a first upgrade of the software in 2016/17, is as follows:

A. Positioning of the ContainerMover at the right lateral position rel. to the wagon (Six sequential steps)

Figure 7 – Wagon adaptor with “cross hairs sign” for positioning

	Where to act / to look	joy-stick	What action to do
1.	Screen in Cab		◆ switch to side camera for positioning at the railway wagon (at cross hairs sign)
2.	Remote Control		◆ switch to : height Mover-Console
3.	Marking line on platform		→ drive parallel to the marking line on the railway platform
4.	Choose right slot on railway wagon (screen in cab)		● halt in front of container slot ◆ lift the Mover-Console until you see the level of the wagon adaptor on the screen
5.	To position the ContainerMover truck exactly at the container slot (screen in cab)		→ slowly advance with truck ◆ steer the truck in parallel position (both front and rear distances should be equal) ◆ place the cross on screen on the cross hair sign of the wagon adaptor (figure1)
6.	Block the ContainerMover truck		◆ initiate the parking brake

Figure 8 – Screen shot (ready for transshipment)

When the cross of the screen is on the hair sign cross of the wagon adaptor and the measured distances to the wagon adaptor at the front and back are the same (with 1cm tolerance), the system is ready for transshipment

After the positioning of the ContainerMover truck, the driver takes the remote control and steps out of his cab to start the next phase: **the horizontal transshipment**

B. The horizontal transshipment

For the horizontal transshipment, there are two situations:

1. Transshipment of a container from the truck to railway wagon, and
2. Transshipment of a container from the railway wagon, to the truck.

These two movements, with its actions to be taken by the driver, are described in detail on the next two pages.

Figure 9 – The remote control, the driver is using

8 Steps to shift a container or swap body from the ContainerMover to the wagon:

Steps (to initiate)		Switch-mode		Procedure/Action	S	step selection joy stick	S	Important to watch/note
1.	open twist-Locks	Twist-locks	fr + r	open twist locks				check if all twist locks are in open position
2.	Lower hydraulic feet	Hydr. Feet		short push to joy stick upwards then let go				conical wedge at the rear of truck will go down
			all	push joy stick upwards again and holt it until feet are firmly down		all feet are on the ground and vehicle is pushed up 4 cm		
	align Mover Consoles	Mover-Consoles	fr + r	alignment to horizontal position		automatic execution		If necessary you can interfere to change angle
3.	to connect the contact bridges to the waggon adaptor	Contact Bridge	fr + r	push joy stick upwards and holt it (automatic stop)		Attention: check the relative height position of contact bridge to waggon adaptor! Commence with 3 cm above wagon adaptor		
		Mover-Consoles	fr + r	push joy stick downwards until the contact bridges are down on the waggon adaptor			Attention: lower both contact bridges onto wagon adaptor. Look at front and rear contact bridge, and apply just a light pressure with contact bridge.	
4.	Lift SB/Container	Mover Beam-Lift	fr + r	push joy stick upwards until sign is green (full lift container)		Container will be lifted from pins Attention: Level 1: container up to 10t / Level 2: 11- 16 tons.		
5.	Transhipment of SB/Container to the waggon	Mover-Transhipment	fr + r	push joy stick upwards and holt it (automatic stop)			Transhipment is halted at 2/3 of stretch in order to automatically adjust the rel. level of Mover against Wagon adaptor (caused by tilt-movement of wagon)	
			fr + r	intermediate level check		automatic execution		
			fr + r	push joy stick upwards again holt it (automatic stop)			Mover will automatically stop when container is exactly over the 4 pins on waggon adaptor	
6.	Lower SB/Container on Waggon	Mover Beam-Lift	fr + r	short push downwards to joy stick and release		Moverbeams (+container) will be lowered. Container descents onto the 4 pins. Check if this is the case at all 4 corners		
7.	returning the Mover-beams back to the truck	Mover-Transhipment	fr + r	push joy stick downwards until automatic stop			Mover Beams will run back to the truck (last 10 cm automatically in slow motion)	
8.	returning the contact bridges to the truck + retraction of hydraulic. feet + lowering mover consoles (tidying up in order to drive away)	Contact Bridge	fr + r	push joy stick downwards until automatic stop			Contact bridges are automatically retracted	
			all			automatic execution		hydraulic feet are automatically retracted automatic lowering of mover consoles
Ready for driving!								

Figure 10 – 8 Steps to shift a container from the ContainerMover to the wagon

8 Steps to shift a container or swap body from the wagon to the ContainerMover:

<i>Steps (to initiate)</i>		<i>Switch-mode</i>		<i>Procedure/Action</i>	S	<i>step selection joy stick</i>	S	<i>Important to watch/note</i>	
1. Lower hydraulic feet		Hydr. Feet		short push to joy stick upwards then let go				conical wedge at the rear of truck will go down	
			all	push joy stick upwards again and holt it until feet are firmly down		all feet are on the ground and vehicle is pushed up 4 cm			
<i>align Mover Consoles</i>		<i>Mover-Consoles</i>	fr + r	<i>alignment to horizontal position</i>		automatic execution		If necessary you can interfere to change angle	
2. to connect the contact bridges to the waggon adaptor		Contact Bridge	fr + r	push joy stick upwards and holt it (automatic stop)		Attention: check the relative height position of contact bridge to waggon adaptor! Commence with 3 cm above wagon adaptor			
		Mover-Consoles	fr + r	push joy stick downwards until the contact bridges are down on the waggon adaptor			Attention: lower both contact bridges onto wagon adaptor. Look at front and rear contact bridge, and apply just a light pressure with contact bridge.		
3 Push moverbeams from CM under container on waggon adaptor		Mover-Transhiment	fr + r	push joy stick upwards and holt it (automatic stop)		Mover will automatically stop when beams are exactly symetrical under the container			
4. Lift Container		Mover Beam-Lift	fr + r	push joy stick upwards until sign is green (full lift container)		Container will be lifted from pins on waggon Attention: Level 1: container up to 10t / Level 2: 11- 16 tons.			
5. Transhiment of Container to the waggon		Mover-Transhiment	fr + r	push joy stick upwards and holt it (automatic stop)				Transhiment is halted at 2/3 of stretch in order to automatically adjust the rel. level of Mover against Wagon adaptor (caused by tilt-movement of wagon)	
			fr + r	<i>intermediate level check</i>		automatic execution			
			fr + r	push joy stick upwards again holt it (automatic stop)			Mover will automatically stop when container is exactly over the 4 pins on ContainerMover		
6. Lower Container on ContainerMover		Mover Beam-Lift	fr + r	short push downwards to joy stick and release		Moverbeams (+container) will be lowered. Container descents onto the 4 pins. Check if this is the case at all 4 corners			
7. Returning the contact bridges to the truck		Contact Bridge	fr + r	push joy stick downwards until automatic stop			Contact bridges are automatically retracted		
<i>retraction of hydraulic feet</i>			all			automatic execution		<i>The hydraulic feet are retracted automatically</i>	
<i>lowering of consoles</i>			fr + r			automatic execution		<i>Consoles are lowered automatically</i>	
8. Closing of twistlocks		Twist-locks	v + h	closing				check if all twist locks are in closed position	
Ready for driving!									

Figure 11 – 8 Steps to shift a container from the wagon to the ContainerMover

2.3 Next steps to come to fully automatic transshipment

Introduction

As can be seen from the two handling-processes for the horizontal transfer, the driver is initiating the different steps of the transshipment process, but the system then runs the steps itself and ends a movement automatically when an end-position is reached. After each step is finished, the driver initiates the next step.

In order to come to a fully automatic loop it would only be necessary to connect the different actions in one single movement. This would be possible if there was not one action that still needed active guidance by the driver.

Problem to overcome

The only action where an active control from the driver is required is when the contact bridge is to be positioned on the wagon adaptor. This needs to be done with active eye surveillance and active steering of the height of the consoles and the relative length of both the contact bridges.

Figure 12 – The contact bridge between ContainerMover and Wagon Adaptor

The reason we were not able to automate this step was the fact that the relative height of the wagon against the truck is not a fix parameter but, differs with the wagon type and the local situation of street surface height against the rail tracks.

Until now, we were able to measure the horizontal distances between the truck and the wagon accurately, but not its relative vertical height against the wagon.

The solution to this problem will be described in the next chapter.

3. Development of full automation of transshipment

3.1 Introduction

As described in Chapter two, we needed to concentrate on the automation of one step in the horizontal transfer process where the surveillance of the drivers was still actively required:

The vertical positioning of the two contact bridges on the wagon adaptor,
Which is presented on the next picture:

Figure 13 – Adjusting the height of the two “contact bridges”

3.2 First the horizontal distance measuring

Up to now we were able to measure the horizontal distance between ContainerMover and wagon (wagon adaptor) accurately using standard ultrasonic sensors. Since 2015, we have been using them on all our delivered ContainerMovers.

Figure 14 – The screen in the cab and one of the ultrasonic sensors

The relative distance to the wagon is automatically measured both at the front and at the back of the Containermover.

This distance is then used to determine the necessary length the contract bridge has to be ejected towards the wagon adaptor to cover the distance between Containermover and wagon adaptor. As the contact bridge is pushed out by hydraulic cylinder, we can use integrated cylinder position measurement (linear encoder) to arrive at the exact position at the wagon adaptor.

Figure 15 – the linear encoder for measuring the exact distance the contract bridge is ejected.

3.3 Introduction of an “intelligent” Camera

As explained in the previous paragraph, the steering of horizontal position of the contract bridge has been solved. The greater challenge was the steering of the vertical position of the contract bridge against the relative height of the wagon adaptor.

After much discussion and extensive research on this topic, we decided on the use the method of digital image reading. This method is used in the industry to help robots to position their tools and recognize objects and their relative position. If we would be able to define the exact position of the “cross-hair-sign” on the wagon adaptor, we would also be able to position the ContainerMover truck in a three-dimensional way.

The process would be the same as done previously by the driver: Instead of the human eye and brain, the camera and the software are giving the information for the steering.

It is necessary to perform this measurement at both sides (front and rear) of the truck, so there are two cameras needed. The steering and controlling of the height at the front console and that of the rear console must be done independently from each other as there is no guarantee that road and rail track are 100% parallel to each other.

After some discussions with suppliers and first tests, we decided on a high-resolution VCXG-53M.I camera from the manufacturer Baumer Electric AG (Switzerland) in combination with the image reading and image analysis software from National Instruments.

The first test was a “dry” test in order to see if the software was able to detect our standard image and to detect its exact relative position to the camera measured in mm, both on the horizontal as vertical axis.

Figure 16 – “dry tests” of the camera and software

Having positive results from this dry test we did a next test with a ContainerMover in Bern.

Figure 17 – field test of camera and software

In a next step, we have equipped a new ContainerMover with a complete set of two cameras and further necessary hardware:

- 2x Baumer Industry camera VCXG-53M.I
- 2x IP-hardcover for protection
- 2x Lens: Kowa LM8HC 8mm/f1.4
- 2x Filter <780nm block 1“-32 H2,5mm
- 2x Infra-red led light
- 1x Industry PC Fabrimec S-SPC-352019022018200
- necessary cables and plugs

Figure 18 – Industry camera Baumer VCXG-53M.I

This hardware has then be built into a Innovatrain ContainerMover :

Figure 19 –ContainerMover with two high solution cameras and two ultrasonic sensors

Figure 20 – high solution cameras and the infra-red support light

Having extensive experience with the use of normal digital cameras for the manual position we also decided to use the infrared light-spectrum in addition to the normal spectrum. The reason for this is that the ContainerMover has to operate in all weather conditions, at night times as well in full sun light conditions. Especially for the last situation, with its possible sunlight reflections, the infrared spectrum gave us very good and stable results.

4. Full automatic horizontal transshipment

4.1 New process of automatic horizontal transshipment

A. Positioning of the ContainerMover at the right lateral position rel. to the wagon

The procedure of the positioning of the ContainerMover truck is not much affected by the automation, because we will not interfere with the steering of the truck.

Figure 21 – Wagon adaptor with “cross hairs sign” for positioning

Process of Positioning the ContainerMover-Truck at the railway wagon

	Where to act / to look	joy-stick	What action to do
1.	Screen in Cab		◆ switch to side camera for positioning at the railway waggon (at cross hairs sign)
2.	Marking line on platform		→ drive parallel to the marking line on the railway platform
3.	Choose right slot on railway wagon (screen in cab)		● halt in front of container slot ◆ lift the Mover-Console until you see the level of the wagon adaptor on the screen
4.	 To position the ContainerMover truck exactly at the container slot (screen in cab)		→ slowly advance with truck ◆ steer the truck in parallel position (both front and rear distances should be equal) ◆ The correct position is reached at the moment the red cross appears on the screen
6.	Block the ContainerMover truck		◆ initiate the parking brake

Figure 22 – Process of Positioning the ContainerMover-Truck at the railway wagon

After blocking the ContainerMover with its parking brake the process of automated horizontal transshipment can be started.

B. The horizontal transshipment automated

The process is started from the screen (Tablet):

Steps	Switch-mode	operation performed
0. Start Transshipment by pushing the start button on the screen	keep joystick in forward position	Transshipment is started
1. Open twist locks	;	the 4 twistlocks are automatically opened
2. Lower hydraulic feet	;	conical wedge at the rear of truck will go down, all feet are on the ground and vehicle is pushed up 4 cm
3. Align Mover Consoles	;	If necessary you can interfere to change angle
4. Connect the contact bridges to the waggon adaptor	;	The contact bridge is pushed the exact length to the wagon adaptor in a position of 2 cm above the contact plate of the wagon adaptor . In a next step, the two consoles are lowered until the contact bridge is on the wagonadaptor.
5. Push moverbeams from CM under container on waggon adaptor	;	Mover will automatically stop when beams are exactly under the container
6. Lift Container	;	Container will be lifted from pins on waggon
7. Transshipment of Container to the waggon	;	Transshipment is halted at 2/3 of stretch in order to automatically adjust the rel. level of Mover against Wagon adaptor (caused by tilt-movement of wagon) Mover will automatically stop when container is exactly over the 4 pins on ContainerMover
8. Lower Container on ContainerMover	;	Moverbeams (+container) will be lowered. Container descends onto the 4 pins. Check if this is the case at all 4 corners
9. Returning the contact bridges to the truck	;	Contact bridges are automatically retracted
10. retraction of hydraulic feet	;	The hydraulic feet are retracted automatically
11. lowering of consoles	;	Consoles are lowered automatically
12. Closing twist locks	let loose of joystick	check if all twist locks are in closed position
Ready for driving!		

Figure 24 – Process of automatic transshipment

During the transshipment procedure, the 12 above steps will be displayed on the screen:

Figure 25 – lay out of the screen in the cab

5. Conclusion

The CargoMover demonstrated the full operational readiness in a classical layout. With the use of digital image reading, we were able to overcome the major hurdle of the different relative wagon heights the ContainerMover is confronted with.

The driver still has to steer the truck to the indicated position at the train and after initiating the parking brake, he can start the transshipment. In principle the driver can stay in his driving cab, but we strongly advise that the driver must step out to keep a close eye at the actual performance of the horizontal transshipment. Not only can there be interference from objects lying around on wagons, there could be other people standing close the transshipment, with all its consequences. During the transshipment process, the driver needs to actively push and hold the joystick on his remote control in the forward position. Releasing this button immediately stops the process. In this way the safety of the process is guaranteed.

A fully automated horizontal transshipment is now technically available for CLUSTERS 2.0 WP4 demonstration in living Lab 3 meeting all major requirements. The breakthrough within work package 4.4 has been the new capability of the ContainerMover-system to recognize its exact relative position to the railway wagon, both in a horizontal as vertical way.

The purpose for 4.4., to make the horizontal transshipment technique; affordable, reliable, fast and easy to use.